

A STUDY ON THE CORRELATION BETWEEN LEARNING STYLES AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF B. ED DISTANCE LEARNERS

Yamini Salian

Seva Sadan's College of Education, Ulhasnagar – 421003

Email: yamini.salian@yahoo.co.in

Paper Received On: 23 May 2023

Peer Reviewed On: 25 May 2023

Published On: 1 June 2023

Abstract

In order to prepare the country for the challenges of the twenty-first century, the New Education Policy [1986] reinterpreted education's role as an instrument for the development of the country's human resources. One of the many inventive solutions included in this new policy is distance learning. According to the New Education Policy, lifelong learning is a desired educational goal. Education and learning style are closely linked because the way individuals learn can greatly impact their educational experience. An individual's preferred method of obtaining and processing information is referred to as their learning style. There are several different theories and models of learning styles, but some of the most common include visual, auditory, logical and kinesthetic/tactile. Numerous initiatives to conduct learning style research have been made in the 19th century. According to numerous studies, every person has a unique learning style, and various learning styles can affect how students "perceive, recall, understand, and solve problems" (Messick, 1976). Teachers must offer material in a manner that suits students' preferences if students desire a greater say in how it is presented; otherwise, their efforts will be futile (Gregoric, 1985). Researchers tried to identify and isolate specific characteristics of the learners in an effort to characterise the distinctive processes of learning (Keefe, 1987; Messick, 1976). For the present research, only four types of learning styles have been taken into consideration that includes visual, auditory, kinesthetic and logical. The present study was done to know the correlation between learning styles and academic achievement of B.Ed. distance learners. The sample size for the present study was comprised of 300 B.Ed. distance learners from YCMOU and IGNOU. The Tools used for collecting the data were the Learning style scale and Academic Achievement Results of the Students. Data were analysed by using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation. A significant correlation between the learning styles of English and Marathi medium was found. It was also found that there was no effect of learning style on Academic Achievement of B.Ed. distance learners as per Gender, age, or with regards to type of school. Conceptual definition of learning style- The way a person naturally or habitually acquires and processes information in a learning environment is referred to as their learning style. The cognitive, emotive, and physiological aspects of a person's capacity for learning are included in their learning styles. (Bodi, 1990) Operational definition of learning style - Learning styles here would be a set of observable characteristics or behaviours that indicate how an individual prefers to learn. There can be various learning styles. Here four types of learners have been looked into that is Visual, Auditory, Kinesthetic and Logical.

Keywords: Learning style, Academic achievement, B.Ed. distance learners

[Scholarly Research Journal's](http://www.srjis.com) is licensed Based on a work at www.srjis.com

Introduction

There are numerous indicators of academic achievement, including extremely broad ones like procedural and declarative information gained via schooling, more curricular ones like grades or performance on an educational achievement test, and cumulative ones like educational degrees and certificates. The fact that each criterion represents intellectual activities makes them all roughly reflective of an individual's intellectual capacity. Academic success is significant to everyone's life in developed societies. Academic achievement as measured by the GPA (grade point average) or by standardised tests designed for selection reasons, such as the SAT (Scholastic Assessment Test), determines whether a student will be granted the opportunity to continue their education (e.g., to attend a university). As a result, academic achievement defines a person's eligibility for higher education and, depending on the educational degrees a person receives, influences their decision regarding their field of employment once they graduate. In addition to its importance for the individual, academic accomplishment is essential for the wealth and development of a country. Given the significance of academic accomplishment for both individuals and society as a whole, it is not unexpected that many scientists, including those in the fields of psychology and education, have focused their research on this topic.

Need and Significance of the study

With the advent of technology, it becomes imperative in today's world to understand how learners adapt to various styles and how it impacts them. So, an advent of curiosity led to this research which rose from the idea that how are learning style and academic achievement related. What difference does it make when one is a distance learner compared to a regular college student? The researcher desires to know the correlation between learning style and academic achievement. The researcher has conducted a present study to know the relationship between learning styles and academic achievement of B Ed distance learners.

Objectives of the study

1. To study the learning styles of B Ed distance learners
2. To study the relationship between learning styles and academic achievement of B Ed distance learners.
3. To study the relationship between learning styles and academic achievement in B Ed distance learners with regards to i) age ii) gender iii) medium of instruction

Hypothesis of the Study

1. There is no significant relationship between learning styles and academic achievement of B Ed distance learners.
2. There is no significant relationship between learning styles and academic achievement of B Ed distance learners; i) age ii) gender iii) medium of instruction

Delimitation of the study

1. This study is limited to B Ed students of IGNOU and YCMOU.
2. This study is limited to B Ed students of English and Marathi mediums.
3. This study is limited to IGNOU and YCMOU B Ed study centres of the Mumbai region.

Methodology used for the study

The investigator selected quantitative research for the present study. The study is based on the effect of the learning styles of B. Ed distance learners on academic achievement. The investigator used the Purposive and Convenient Sampling method and selected 300 distance learners from IGNOU and YCMOU learning centres.

Sample of the study

The researcher selected 300 B.Ed. distance learners randomly from English and Marathi as the final sample size for the present study.

Tools used for the study

The researcher used the following tools for the present study;

Learning statements were selected from various books, research journals, and articles. Statements were collected on the basis of learning styles. After choosing the statements, a few statements were rejected which were not suitable. All statements were arranged and each statement was related to one another and they were divided on the basis of different types of learning styles.

The learning style scale was prepared in English and Marathi language. The reliability of learning style scale is 0.83 the learning style scale comprised 34 items, having statements comprising of Visual, Auditory, and Kinesthetic and Logical learners. The options for giving answers to all the 34 items in the learning style scale were given in the form of 'Yes' and 'No'. The students had to put a tick mark against one of the options. The students were given a score of 2 for Yes and 1 score for No

(2) The result in the form of a percentage was used to know the academic achievement of the selected B.Ed. distance learners for the present study.

Statistical Analysis

(1) Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Technique was used by the investigator to study the co-relation between learning styles and academic achievement of B Ed distance learners as per Gender, age, type of school and medium of instruction separately.

Table 1 shows Learning style and Academic Achievement mean score and standard deviation as per background variables.

Correlation	Variable	N	Pearson's Co-efficient Correlation Calculated r value	Pearson's Co-efficient Correlation Tabulated r value	Result
Learning style and Academic Achievement	English	150	0.237	0.1592 at 0.05 level 0.2083 at 0.01 level	Significant at 0.05 and 0.01 level
	Marathi	150	0.221	0.2083	Significant at 0.01 level

Findings

The findings obtained from the present research were;

1. A significant correlation between the learning styles of B Ed distance learners from English medium and academic achievement was obtained
2. A significant correlation between the learning styles of B Ed distance learners from Marathi medium and academic achievement was obtained

It was found that gender and age did not have a significant effect on the Academic achievement of B.Ed. distance learners.

Conclusion

It can be seen that there is a correlation between the English and Marathi B.Ed distance learners' learning styles and their academic achievement based on the findings. It is possible that English and Marathi medium learners may differ in their learning styles due to a variety of factors such as cultural, social, and educational backgrounds. However, it is important to note that learning styles can vary greatly among individuals regardless of their language medium. It is also important to consider the teaching styles of instructors, as this can greatly influence the learning styles of students. Teachers who use a variety of teaching methods and techniques can better cater to the diverse learning styles of their students

References

- Best, John W. and Kahn, J. V. (2007). *Research in Education*, New Delhi, Prentice Hall of India Private.
- Biswas, P.K. (1999) *Freshers in IGNOU: A study of their awareness, interest and motivation*, *Indian Journal of open learning* 8(3) 273-282 Crow, R.D. and A. Crow,
- Chandra, Subhash (2017). *Study of learning styles and process of development of professional skills among students of professional courses of open universities*. Ph.D Thesis, University of Allahabad.
- Fatt, J. P. (2000). *Understanding the learning styles of students*. *International Journal of Sociology and Social Policy*, 20(11), 31-45.
- Sharma R.A (2008). *Distance education*, Meerut: International publishing house

Online References

- <https://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in:8443/>
- <https://materchristi.libguides.com/c.php?g=169439&p=1114508>
- <https://www.learning-styles-online.com/style/solitary-intrapersonal/>